

**ATTITUDES AND POSSIBILITIES OF APPLICATION OF
ISLAMIC METHODS OF BUYING AN
APARTMENT/PROPERTY IN NOVI PAZAR AND THE
REPUBLIC OF SERBIA THROUGH THE SYSTEM OF
DIMINISHING PARTNERSHIP (MUSHARAKA MUTANAQISA)**

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Abstract

The area of the Balkans, in general (from Turkey to Croatia), caught the "fever" of building construction after the world economic crisis (2008). Especially big cities like Belgrade, Sarajevo, Zagreb, and Podgorica started to get modern residential and business blocks. However, smaller cities such as Novi Pazar in the Sandžak region, in the Republic of Serbia, are also covered by the trend of massive residential construction and transformation from an area characterized by houses to an area with a large number of buildings. The reasons for this in general in the Balkans should be sought in the impossibility or lack of knowledge of capital investment in modern flows (funds, shares, etc.).

However, this is not the topic of this paper, because the topic is to investigate attitudes and possibilities of applying Islamically acceptable and ethically correct ways of buying real estate. For this reason, this paper will present the results of a survey on how the citizens of Novi Pazar and the wider area evaluate the need for Islamic ways of buying real estate through the institute of contractual relationship "diminishing partnership" (Musharaka Mutanaqisa). The idea is that through the current legislation, like Bosnia and Herzegovina, citizens of all denominations are offered the Islamically correct concept of buying an apartment with deferred payment, but also to measure attitudes and opinions about the idea of establishing an institute/organization/bank that would offer such products. The goal is to measure the attitudes of the population in Novi Pazar, which is predominantly Islamic, and the attitudes of citizens in the wider area of the Republic of Serbia, which is predominantly Orthodox Christian.

Keywords: Housing construction, sale of real estate, loan, interest-free loan, Diminishing Musharaka (Musharaka Mutanaqisa).

INTRODUCTION

Following the global economic crisis of 2008, the Balkans, stretching from Turkey to Croatia, experienced a surge in construction activity. Major urban centers like Belgrade, Sarajevo, Zagreb, and Podgorica saw a rapid emergence of modern residential and business complexes. Smaller cities, such as Novi Pazar in Serbia's Sandžak region, have also been swept up in this trend, transitioning from predominantly single-family homes to increasingly dense apartment buildings. This construction boom across the Balkans can be partially attributed to limited knowledge

of alternative investment opportunities, like funds or stocks, which might have otherwise diverted capital flows.

Serbia experienced a significant construction surge. Table 1 shows the percentage of GDP attributed to two sectors in Serbia from 2008 to 2023, Construction and Real Estate Business. So trends of Indicator F construction, show the share of construction in GDP fluctuated, starting at 4.4% in 2008, decreasing until 2013 to a low of 3.0%, and then increasing steadily. The highest value was in 2019, with construction reaching 5.7% of GDP before the Covid 19 crisis. Recent years (2021-2023) saw moderate values, with construction contributing around 5.0% of GDP. Second Indicator L- Real Estate Business, had a more stable contribution to GDP, starting at 7.8% in 2008 and peaking at 9.0% in 2009. It generally declined over the years, reaching a low of 6.9% in 2020 and again in 2022. In 2023, real estate business contributed 7.2% to GDP. This data reflects the dynamics of Serbia's economic landscape, particularly in construction and real estate, with notable growth in construction in recent years, indicating possible development or infrastructure expansion efforts. (Bajramović, 2023 and Statistical Serbia Report 2024)

Table 1
GROSS ADDED VALUE BY ACTIVITIES OF REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

Period	REPUBLIC OF SERBIA															
	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Data type	Gross added value by activities															
Indicator	Share in GDP %															
F - Construction	4.4	3.6	3.4	3.8	3.8	3.0	3.2	3.8	3.9	4.1	4.5	5.7	4.7	5.2	4.8	5.0
L - Real estate business	7.8	9.0	8.7	7.8	7.8	7.8	8.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	7.7	6.9	7.7	7.7	6.9	7.2

Source: <https://www.stat.gov.rs/sr-latn/vesti/statisticalrelease/?p=15314>

Construction is a crucial business activity for any country, including those in the Balkan region. In Western economies and most countries, the sale of construction products (such as apartments, stores, and garage spaces) is closely tied to banks, credit placements, and loan offers for companies involved in construction or real estate trading. Although a significant portion of the Balkan population is Islamic, there are not many Islamic-compliant financing options for purchasing real estate. Except for Bosnia and Herzegovina and Turkey, which offer some Islamic banking products, other countries with Islamic populations—such as Serbia, Montenegro, Kosovo*, and Albania—do not provide such financial services.

BBi Bank's notable use of TKL financing in the Republika Srpska entity demonstrates that the bank actively implements these models across Bosnia and Herzegovina, not just in the Federation of B&H, where the Muslim population is concentrated. This

approach challenges the stereotype that Islamic banking products are only utilized by Muslims. Furthermore, this type of financing encouraged clients to deepen their relationship with BBI by exploring products beyond TKL, illustrating that BBI's commitment to CSR yielded tangible financial benefits. (Zogić et al., 2024)

SURVEY: ATTITUDE RESEARCH OF AWARENESS AND WILLINGNESS TO USE THE "MUSHARAKA MUTANAQISA" MODEL IN SERBIA AND THE CITY OF NOVI PAZAR

Big changes have taken place in the field of construction after the world crisis of 2008. However, as shown in Table No. 2, we separately watch the region of Novi Pazar and the rest of Serbia because they have different religious and social perspectives. That's why we decided to conduct surveys of the population's attitudes about awareness and willingness to use the "Musharaka Mutanaqisa" model in the territory of Serbia and the city of Novi Pazar for the purposes of this work. The reason why we did not decide on the wider area of Kosovo, Albania, and North Macedonia concerns the language barrier. The sample of surveys was more than 100 so it can be shown as statistically correct. As can be seen in Table no. 2, the total number of respondents is about 229 in the rest of the Republic of Serbia and the response was the highest in the first two days of the survey, the number 249 was reached at the end, but 229 is used for analysis.

Table 2
TWO SAMPLE SURVEY

	Serbia	Novi Pazar city
Sample N	229	103
model of collecting data	Online survey	Online survey
Link	https://forms.gle/Ce67fDiowGqawbo78	https://forms.gle/D6SYyfEcn0TEkJvr7
Promoted	free promotion	Facebook/ Instagram
Date	25.08-29.08.2024	23.08-29.08.2024

Source: Authors on data of two surveys (2024)

The aim was to conduct a nearly identical survey across all the mentioned areas, including the city of Novi Pazar. Why Novi Pazar? This city has the youngest population in Europe but also faces one of the highest unemployment rates, approximately 50%. According to unofficial data and media reports, 23,265 people are unemployed. Official unemployment figures are calculated at the regional level, including Raška and Kraljevo, where unemployment is below 10%, which skews the regional average to around 11%, masking the real situation in Novi Pazar.

Another reason for selecting Novi Pazar is its role as a trading hub for nearby cities such as Tutin, Sjenica, Priboj, and Nova Varoš in Serbia, as well as Rožaje, Berane,

Plav, and Gusinje in Montenegro. Additionally, Novi Pazar serves as an academic center, attracting a large number of students from the Sandžak region, which spans northern Montenegro and southwestern Serbia.

Moreover, the city of Novi Pazar as a whole region of the Balkans is experiencing a rapid increase in construction, particularly in residential and commercial buildings. This growth is driven by the rising demand for housing and business spaces, fueled by the younger population and the influx of students. However, challenges such as the affordability of housing and the availability of financing options, including those compliant with Islamic principles, remain significant issues. These factors make Novi Pazar a unique case for studying attitudes toward modern financial models and urban development trends in the region.

Novi Pazar as a region stands out with a significant increase in the number of completed apartment units and population growth over the past two decades. Between 2001 and 2010, 943 apartment units were completed, while in the period from 2011 to 2021, this number rose to 3,210, representing an impressive growth of 340%. At the same time, the population grew from 100,410 in 2001 to 107,859 in 2021, an increase of 7.42% (Bajramović, 2023). One of the couple of regions that had increased. These figures indicate a rising demand for residential space and substantial investments in apartment construction, supported by positive demographic trends in this region. The population growth further supports the idea of expanding apartment needs in this area.

For these reasons, it was important to compare the perspectives of citizens from Novi Pazar with those from other parts of Serbia. Table 3 shows us how these two samples have different ways of living. For example, in the Novi Pazar sample, 65% of respondents live in houses, only 26.9% do not have children, and 54.8% live with their parents, with a monthly income between €1,000 and €1,500. In contrast, in the sample from the rest of Serbia, 75.2% identify as Orthodox Christians, 71.1% live in apartments, 50% do not have children, and 75.2% do not live with their parents, with a monthly income exceeding €2,000.

So it was very important to see how these samples have views on the same things: attitudes about awareness and willingness to use the "Musharaka Mutanaqisa" model in the territory of Serbia and the city of Novi Pazar. So the hypothesis is made this way.

The hypothesis that is set as H0 proposes that *citizens who are of the Islamic faith are interested in applying Islamic methods of real estate purchase. However, they may forgo this option upon learning that, under the Musharakah Mutanaqisah system, the majority owner of the property is the bank. In contrast, citizens of the Orthodox faith are expected to show no interest in such financial products.*

Table 3
MOST COMMON ANSWERS IN TWO SURVEYS

No.	Question in Survey	Largest % Answers in Novi Pazar Sample	Largest % Answers in Serbia Sample
1	Religion	98.1% (Islam)	75.2% (Orthodox Christian)
2	Age	43.3% (30-40 years)	43.5% (30-40 years)
3	Gender	60.6% (Male)	83.7% (Male)
4	Education	38.5% (University degree)	36.2% (University degree)
5	Marital Status	76% (Married)	55.3% (Married)
6	Children	26.9% (No children)	50% (No children)
7	Living with parents	54.8% (Living with parents)	75.2% (Not living with parents)
8	Housing type	65.4% (House)	71.1% (Apartment)
9	Homeownership	74% (Owner)	65% (Owner)
10	Monthly family income	35.6% (€1,000–1,500)	52.4% (Over €2,000)
11	Familiarity with Islamic Financial Products	45.2% (Partly familiar)	48% (Not informed)
12	Awareness of interest-free Financing Options	76% (Familiar)	50.8% (Unaware)
13	Method of Financing Real Estate Purchase	44.2% (Cash)	60.2% (Bank loan)
14	Interest in Interest-Free Financing	76% (Sounds interesting)	71.1% (Sounds interesting)
15	Key Factor in Choosing Financing Method Preferred Source of	54.8% (Religious compliance)	43.1% (Total cost)
16	Information about Islamic Financing	48.1% (Internet)	59.3% (Internet)
17	Willingness to Use Islamic Banking Agreement on	66.3% (Would use it)	65.9% (Depends on conditions)
18	Supporting Islamic Financial Products Awareness of the	76.9% (Totally agree)	44.7% (Totally agree)
19	"Musharaka Mutanaqisa" Model Interest in "Musharaka	54.8% (Not aware)	66.3% (Not aware)
20	Mutanaqisa" Model Despite Complexity	45.2% (Very interesting)	41.8% (Potentially interesting)

Source: data from two surveys

Table 4

*SPSS COMPARISON OF QUESTIONS 13 AND 20 (13.The most common way of financing procurement of real estate? * 20. Musharaka Mutanaqisa (diminishing partnership) you own as much % of the real estate as you bought from the bank)*

13. Most common way of financing procurement of real estate?		a. Cash			Count	20. With Musharaka Mutanaqis (diminishing partnership) you own as much as % of the real estate
		% of Total	you own as much % of the property as you bought	% within 13. Most common way of financing procurement of real estate?		
		0,4%	50,0%	1,6%	1	a. Very interested
		10,0%	24,5%	37,7%	23	b. Somewhat interested
		10,0%	24,5%	37,7%	23	c. I wasn't interested.
		2,6%	40,0%	9,8%	6	d. I stopped being interested
		0,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0	e. I'm not sure, I need more information
		3,5%	34,8%	13,1%	8	
		26,6%	26,6%	100,0%	61	Total

Total		d. Other				
		% of Total	you own as much % of the property as you bought	% within 13. Most common way of financing procurement of real estate?	Count	
0,9%	100,0%	0,9%	100,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0
41,0%	100,0%	41,0%	100,0%	1,3%	3,2%	3
41,0%	100,0%	41,0%	100,0%	2,6%	6,4%	6
6,6%	100,0%	6,6%	100,0%	0,4%	6,7%	1
0,4%	100,0%	0,4%	100,0%	0,0%	0,0%	0
10,0%	100,0%	10,0%	100,0%	0,9%	8,7%	2
100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	100,0%	5,2%	5,2%	12

Source: Authors data from SPSS

RESULTS

The survey that was conducted in Novi Pazar and the rest of the Republic of Serbia showed certain differences in general attitudes related to marriage, family, earnings, and property. However, these two samples showed us that they are almost identical in terms of "diminishing partnership" regardless of the different religious groups and ways of life. Thus, out of 229 respondents from the rest of the Republic of Serbia, 139 are users of housing loans, 57 of them completely, and 60 to some extent say that they would like the Musharak Mutanaqis system. In Table 4. therefore 84.17% of home loan users want a "Diminishing Partnership" as a way to finance the purchase of real estate. The results are very encouraging that Islamic banks have a place in the economic system of the Republic of Serbia and the Balkans in general.

The hypothesis set as H0 is not confirmed. Although it was assumed that citizens who are of the Islamic faith are interested in applying Islamic methods of real estate purchase but might give up this option if they discovered that, under the Musharaka Mutanaqis system, the majority owner is the Bank, while citizens of the Orthodox faith were not expected to be interested in such products, the survey results tell a different story. The conducted survey in Novi Pazar and the rest of the Republic of Serbia revealed significant differences in attitudes regarding marriage, family, earnings, and property. However, when it comes to the "diminishing partnership" system, both samples showed similar levels of interest, regardless of different religious affiliations or lifestyles. Specifically, among the 229 respondents from the rest of Serbia, 139 are housing loan users, with 57 fully and 60 partially expressing interest in the Musharaka Mutanaqis system. This means that 84.17% of home loan users are in favor of "Diminishing Partnership" as a method of real estate financing. Other samples of Novi Pazar show us that 45.2% is very interesting in the Musharaka Mutanaqis system. These results highlight the potential for Islamic banking in the Republic of Serbia and the Balkans as a whole.

CONCLUSION

The correct Islamic way of buying real estate implies the absence of interest, but the buyer is charged a margin (earnings) known in advance, which cannot be changed. Saudi Arabia and the United Arab Emirates as part of BRICS use this method in the banking system. In Great Britain, with the unchanged application of domestic legislation, there is the possibility of taking out such loans. Similarly, Bosnia and Herzegovina has implemented these systems. Instead of a conclusion, a possible suggestion is that the Islamic community in Serbia sends an official request for the introduction of Islamic financial products in the Republic of Serbia, such as BBI Bank, To start with Musharak Mutanaqis. This is just an initial idea, and the business community, religious institutions of the Islamic community, banks, and the state need to work together to make this a reality in the future.

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